

Solvent Extraction of Wax from Northern Ireland Lignite

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Recent explorations in Northern Ireland have identified recoverable lignite reserves of 500–1000 million tons. In addition to providing a vast major resource of fuel, these lignite resources offer a rich source of chemical feedstock. In this work the ability of certain solvents to extract waxes from Northern Ireland lignite has been investigated. The influence of solvent type, extraction temperature and contact time has been studied. Exhaustive extraction with toluene shows that Crumlin lignite contains 16.6% (w/w) wax on dry basis.

OVER eighteen countries have reserves of lignitic coal in excess of one billion metric tons, the most important being Russia, America, Australia, Germany and Poland; also included are Canada, Yugoslavia, Czechoslovakia, Chile, Bulgaria, India, Japan, Greece and Hungary. Smaller, though still significant amounts have been found in twentyfive other countries, for example, Turkey, Spain, Burma, Austria, Italy and Pakistan¹.

Deposits in the region of 500–1000 tons of mineable lignite have been proved as a result of exploration work carried out within the last ten years² in Northern Ireland. The existence of these deposits has been known for many years; the Crumlin deposit was first recorded in 1757³. The location of lignite seams in Northern Ireland is shown in Fig. 1. The largest deposits are located in the vicinity of Crumlin, County Antrim, where the recoverable tonnage is in excess of 420 million tonnes². Full mining feasibility and related studies have been completed and initial open-cast strip mining tests have been performed. There are four other lignite sites in Northern Ireland: Ballymoney,

Lough Beg, Coagh and Washing Bay. The Ballymoney and Coagh sites are the most promising of these in mining terms, having about 500 million tonnes of mineable lignite between them.

The main use of lignite is as a fuel but it does offer potential as a chemical feedstock. Lignites contain some waxes and resins, and the aim of this paper is to report on the extraction of lignite waxes from the Crumlin deposits in Northern Ireland. The parameters studied include type of solvent, contact time, and extraction temperature.

Lignitic or montan wax: Strictly, the term montan wax refers only to the material obtained by solvent extraction of suitable German brown coals, montana wax being the more correct, generic description of similar waxes, regardless of geographical origin. However, those small quantities made outside Germany are commonly referred to as montan, prefixed by the name of the country of origin.

Montan wax was first produced commercially in Germany from certain lignites known as 'extraction-skole', and the Riebeck brand of montan wax is well-known. Apart from this product of East German origin, other well-known types of montan wax are the American, from Californian lignite, the Czechoslovakian, the Polish and the Russian montan wax. Crude montan wax is somewhat limited in its application because of its dark colour and excessive amount of resinous and asphaltic matter. It is therefore necessary to remove the resin and asphaltic matter from it and also to lighten its colour.

The chemistry and properties of montan wax depend to a great degree on the material from which it is extracted but all montan wax contains varying amounts of resin and asphalt, depending on the source. The wax component of montan is a mixture of long-chain (C_{24} – C_{30}) esters (62–68 wt%), long-chain acids (22–26 wt%) and long-chain alcohols, ketones and hydrocarbons (7–15 wt%). The resin portion is about 70 wt% terpenes and polyterpenes and 30 wt% resinic acid

Fig. 1. Location of Northern Ireland lignite reserves (specially produced by the Geological Survey of Northern Ireland).

and oxyresinic acid ; the asphalt portion is believed to be polymerised esters of oxyresinic acid⁴.

Commercially, montan wax is obtained by solvent extraction of dried, granulated lignite with nondispersing liquids, such as C₂ or C₄ alcohols, benzene or benzene-alcohol mixtures, with yields of 5-20% wax obtained¹. The yield and composition of this extract are determined primarily by the petrologic character of the lignite rather than by its degree of coalification. The extraction may be carried out under pressure⁵. According to Wagle and Kane⁴, the solvents reported to have been used in the German wax industry include benzene, a mixture of 80% benzene and 20% ethyl alcohol and of 85% benzene and 15% unrefined wood alcohol (containing methyl and isopropyl alcohols). Other solvents cited in literature are benzene-acetone mixture⁶, acetone⁷, tetralin⁸, chlorinated hydrocarbons and aromatic hydrocarbons. Table 1 gives the wax content of lignite from South Ancot (India) when different solvents were used. Work on Greek lignites by Kampouris *et al.*⁹ shows (Table 2) that a mixture of benzene-methanol (50/50, v/v) gives a higher yield of wax in all samples tested than when only benzene was used. Wagle and Kane⁴ performed exhaustive extractions in Soxhlet apparatus using various solvents with lignite from Neyveli (Madras State, India). Their results are shown in Table 3. The results of exhaustive extractions of wax from South Island (New Zealand) lignites, in Soxhlet apparatus performed by Judd and Kemp¹⁰, are given in Table 4. The yields of wax obtained from Crumlin (Northern Ireland) lignite from work with Soxhlet apparatus, carried out by Wilson¹¹ are shown in Table 5.

TABLE 1—YIELD OF WAX FROM SOUTH ANCOT LIGNITE

Solvent	Extracted %
benzene	9.1
Xylene	11.8
Benzene-ethanol	13.7
Pyridine	14.8
Tetralin	11.6

TABLE 2—YIELD OF WAX FROM GREEK LIGNITES*

Mine	Benzene % (dry basis)	Benzene-Methanol (50/50, v/v) % (dry basis)
Allveri	1.2	2.5
Amynteon	1.9	3.9
Dilophon	1.2	3.5
Kalavryta, Palaiochorlon	1.9	3.0
Kalavryta, Xydias	1.6	2.7
Mavrossouvala	0.7	1.8
Magalopolis	1.6	3.0
Pagalon	1.9	5.2
Psachna	3.3	10.2
Protomais	0.8	1.8

*Ref. 9.

TABLE 3—YIELD OF WAX FROM NEYVELI*

Sl. no.	Solvent**	Extract % (dry basis)
1.	Petroleum ether	2.7
2.	Xylene	4.4
3.	Carbon tetrachloride	4.8
4.	Trichloroethylene	4.9
5.	Toluene	6.0
6.	Chloroform	5.7
7.	Methyl alcohol	1.6
8.	Benzene ^a	5.1
9.	Benzene	5.1
10.	Methanol ^b	2.7
11.	Benzene-ethanol azeotrope	9.9
12.	Benzene-ethanol (85=15v/v)	10.4
13.	Benzene ^c	8.8

*Ref. 4. **Extract of: ^athe residue from number 7, ^bthe residue from number 9, ^cnumber 12 re-extracted.

TABLE 4—YIELD OF CRUDE WAX FROM SOUTH ISLAND (NZ) LIGNITE*

Solvent	% Extracted total crude wax	% Composition of crude wax		
		True wax	Resin	Asphalt
Toluene/ethanol/water	11.30	45.1	35.5	19.4
Toluene	7.75	63.7	22.8	13.5
Xylene	6.50	65.5	17.0	17.5
Benzene	6.55	69.7	18.7	11.6
Carbon tetrachloride	5.50	76.6	14.4	9.0
Methyl isobutyl ketone	7.60	49.8	27.8	22.4
Isopropanol	6.85	55.9	29.3	14.8

*Ref. 10.

TABLE 5—YIELD OF CRUDE WAX FROM ANTRIM (NI) LIGNITE*

Solvent	% Extracted (Theoretical)	% Extracted (Actual)
Toluene	10.04	14.52
A-Hexane	6.19	6.69
Benzene	11.61	10.71
Methanol	8.26	—
Methyl isobutyl ketone	9.98	15.25
Chloroform	8.12	13.15
Isopropanol	12.26	12.93
Chloroform-Hexane (3:1)	9.57	12.04

*Ref. 11.

According to Wagle and Kane⁴ the wax and resin extract may be separated by dissolving the crude wax in a solvent and chilling the solution when the wax is precipitated and the resins left in solution. Solvents that have been suggested for this procedure include ethanol⁴, isobutanol¹², methanol¹³, benzene-alcohol¹⁴, ethyl ether¹⁵, benzene-acetone¹⁶, ethyl acetate¹⁷, butyl acetate¹⁸, gasoline¹⁸ and dichloroethane¹⁸.

Chemical composition of montan wax: The approximate composition of central German, crude montan wax has been given as esters of waxy monocarboxylic acids (53%), free waxy monocarboxylic acids (17%), free monohydric alcohols (1-2%), ketones (3-6%), resins (20-23%) and asphaltic

material (3%). The range of carbon numbers for the alcohols and acids, whether free or combined, is C_{22} to about C_{34} , both odd and even numbers being present, but with the latter predominating. C_{26} , C_{28} and C_{30} are often present in the largest amount¹⁰. Lactones, estolides, polyterpenes, and hydrocarbons, mainly paraffinic, have also been found, usually falling within the same range of carbon numbers. In the dark resinous portion various acids and hydroxy-acids, sulphur-containing acids and hydroxy-acid esters, terpenes and sterols have been reported by Wagle and Kane⁴.

Experimental

A sample of lignite was supplied from the Crumlin open cast pit and air-dried for ten days. The lignite was sieved and the size range from 150 to 710 microns was collected and used in all extractions. The characteristics of lignite are presented in Table 6.

TABLE 6—SPECIFICATION OF DRIED ANTRIM LIGNITE

Bulk density	0.6 tonne meter ³ approx.
Proximate analysis	
Moisture (%)	14.0
Ash (%)	10.5
Sulphur (%)	0.2
Chlorine (%)	0.05
Gross CV (kJ kg ⁻¹)	20700
Ultimate analysis	
Weight % (Dry ash-free basis)	
Carbon	69.98
Hydrogen	6.48
Nitrogen	0.65
Sulphur	0.21
Chlorine	0.04
Oxygen (by diff.)	23.34

The solvents used were toluene, xylene and methanol (all AnalaR).

Extraction apparatus: The apparatus was an agitated, baffled batch vessel (4 lit). The extraction temperature was controlled by immersing the extraction vessel in a Grant water-bath (10 lit). Fig. 2 shows the apparatus comprising of eight aluminium baffles and a straight six-bladed impeller (10 cm dia). The agitation speed was maintained constant using a Heidolph electric motor.

In order to measure the wax content of samples, a Rotavapour (Buch) rotary vacuum evaporator was used to evaporate the solvent prior to weighing. Samples (25 ml) were taken at regular time-intervals and the decrease in volume was compensated in the calculations.

Lignite loading: According to Wilson¹¹, a higher % wax extraction is obtained at smaller lignite/solvent ratios, the reason for this being better contact between the lignite and solvent. Judd and

Fig. 2. Extraction apparatus.

Kemp¹⁰ reported an increase in crude wax extraction with increasing lignite/solvent ratio. This is probably due to increasing asphalt extraction due to more intensive attrition occurring at high lignite loadings. It was therefore decided to use a lignite – solvent ratio of 0.4. Thus using 1 kg of lignite, 2500 ml of solvent would be required. The beaker was filled with lignite in which the extraction was to be carried out to about 2/3, leaving sufficient volume to allow for the stirring of the contents. While a lower lignite – solvent ratio might have produced a greater % extraction, it would be offset by the smaller mass of lignite present (in terms of producing a certain mass of wax).

Calculation of percentage extraction: The following assumption were made: (i) the moisture content remains constant throughout each extraction run (for the exhaustive extraction the moisture content was measured between each run and corrected accordingly), (ii) the loss in mass of the lignite due to wax formation and water loss is neglected, and (iii) the water 'released' by the lignite during the extraction has no diluting effect on the mixture.

Total mass of dry lignite at the start of extraction: The mass of dry lignite used in each extraction was calculated as

$$M_1 = \frac{M_0}{1+x}$$

where, x is the moisture content of lignite (dry basis) (kg water/kg dry lignite), M_1 the mass of bone dry lignite (g) and M_0 the mass of 'wet' lignite for extraction (g). The tests all used lignite with a moisture content of 0.193 (dry basis). Thus the

mass of dry lignite in a 1 kg mass of 'wet' lignite was 838.2 g.

Total mass of dry lignite in the vessel at each sampling stage: Each sample from the lignite-solvent mixture contained 10 g lignite with moisture content $x=0.193$ (assumption i). The expression used to calculate the mass of dry lignite in each sample was

$$M_{sd} = \frac{M_{sw}}{1+x}$$

where, M_{sd} is the mass of dry lignite in sample (g), and M_{sw} the mass of 'wet' lignite in sample (g). Thus in a 10 g sample, with moisture content $x=0.193$, the dry mass of lignite was 8.4 g. Hence the mass of dry lignite at each sampling stage was calculated as

$$M_{1t,n} = M_o - \sum_{n=1}^{10} M_{sd}$$

where, $M_{1t,n}$ is the total mass of absolutely dry lignite at each sampling stage n (g).

Total volume of solvent in the vessel at each sampling stage: The total volume of solvent at each sampling stage must be known in order to calculate the total mass of wax at each sampling stage from the weight of wax in the samples. The expressions used to calculate this volume were as follows.

For $T=0-60$ min,

$$V_n = V_o - (T_n \cdot R_o) - \sum_{n=1}^{10} V_{sn}$$

where, V_n is the volume of solvent at each sampling stage n (ml), V_o the initial volume of solvent (ml), T the period of time from the beginning of the run to the time of sampling (min), R_o the evaporation rate of solvent (ml min^{-1}) and V_{sn} the volume of solvent in the sample n (ml).

For $T=60-120$ min,

$$V_n = (V_o + V_c) - (T_n \cdot R_o) - \sum_{n=1}^{10} V_{sn}$$

where, V_c is the volume of fresh solvent added hourly to correct for evaporation (ml).

For $T=120-180$ min,

$$V_n + (V_o + 2 \cdot V_c) - (T_n \cdot R_o) - \sum_{n=1}^{10} V_{sn}$$

Total mass of crude wax at each sampling stage: The following expression was used,¹

$$M_{wt,n} = M_{wn} \cdot \frac{V_n}{V_{sn}}$$

where, $M_{wt,n}$ is the total mass of wax in the vessel at each sampling stage n (g), M_{wn} the mass of wax in sample n (g), V_n the total volume of solvent in the vessel at each sampling stage n (ml) and V_{sn} the volume of solvent in sample n (ml).

Percentage crude wax extracted: The % extraction at each sampling stage was obtained by the following expression,

$$\% \text{ Wax/Lignite} = \frac{M_{wt,n}}{M_{1t,n}} \times 100$$

Results and Discussion

Drying of lignite in air: During the initial studies reported in this paper it was decided to use lignite which had come to equilibrium with the moisture content in air.

As can be observed from Fig. 3, air-drying for about one week is an effective method of drying to equilibrium, provided the moisture content required is not less than about 0.2 kg water/kg dry lignite. After about ten days the moisture content had reached the equilibrium level of 0.16 kg water/kg dry lignite (13.8% water on wet basis). This lignite was used in all extraction tests.

Fig. 3. Drying curve for lignite.

Determination of best solvent for wax extraction from Antrim lignite: Three solvents were chosen from those cited in the literature mainly due to the extraction ability of the solvent but also based on the cost. It was decided not to use solvent mixtures due to the greater difficulty in solvent recovery from the wax-solvent mixture after the extraction process.

Table 7 shows the solvents used, % wax extracted and some properties of the solvents. Fig. 4 shows

TABLE 7—YIELD OF CRUDE WAX EXTRACTED FROM ANTRIM (NI) LIGNITE AND PROPERTIES OF SOLVENTS USED

Solvent	Solvent solubility in water (ml/100 ml)	Solvent b.p. °C	% Crude wax extracted (dry basis)
Toluene	0.0516	110.8	10.9
Xylene	0.0496	138.0	10.1
Methanol	Miscible	64.7	8.5

how the % wax extracted (dry lignite basis) for the different solvents varies with time. Toluene gave the highest % wax extraction, followed by xylene, with methanol giving the lowest.

Fig 4. Plots of % wax extracted vs time: (+) methanol 60°, (—) xylene 70°, (Δ) toluene 70° and (\times) methanol 40°C.

The greater capability of one solvent over another for extracting wax from lignite, must be related to the greater solubility of the solvent with the wax. The high % extraction obtained with toluene is probably due to the presence of an electron-donating group (methyl group) attached to a stable carbonium ion (phenyl) thus ensuring that it has good polarisability and capacity to solvate the ester (53%) and ketone (36%) components of montan wax.

The more insoluble the solvent is in water, the better the solvent for extraction of wax from lignite. This is because less water will be extracted from the lignite and any that is extracted would be easier to remove. Solubility of a non-electrolyte in water depends, to a certain extent, on whether they can form hydrogen bonds with water. Thus the hydrogen-bonding hydroxyl group in methanol contributes to its solubility in water.

Apart from yield of wax extracted by the solvent, there are other factors to consider before making the ultimate choice of solvent. The quality of wax obtained is an important factor. The higher the true wax content in the crude wax the better is the crude wax. No comment can be made on the true wax content of the crude waxes obtained in this investigation as they were not separated into their different components.

Other factors to consider are the solvent toxicity, flammability, reactivity, corrosive power, boiling point, heat of vaporisation, availability and cost.

Effect of temperature: The effect of temperature on % extraction was studied with two solvents.

Tests were carried out with methanol at 40 and 60° and with toluene at 70 and 90°. The % crude wax extracted is plotted against time for the two solvents used at different temperatures (Figs. not shown). Table 8 shows the % crude wax extracted for the different solvents at the different temperatures. For methanol, the % of wax extracted increased with increase in temperature (by about 40% from 40 to 60°).

TABLE 8—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON YIELD OF CRUDE WAX

Solvent	Temp. °C	% Crude wax extracted (dry basis)
Toluene	70	10.8
	90	10.9
Methanol	40	2.0
	60	3.3

Exhaustive extraction: The aim of this procedure was to determine the total crude wax content of the lignite. This was achieved by contacting a batch of lignite with solvent, separating the solvent and lignite and repeating the extraction with a new batch of solvent. A graph of cumulative mass of wax extracted against the number of extractions could then be plotted and the total mass of wax present in the lignite determined by extrapolating this graph to constant cumulative mass of wax. The solvent-lignite mixture was separated by filtration of the hot mixture immediately after the extraction, through a sintered glass filter (no. 3). The solvent was then evaporated to determine the wax content and the lignite was dried for about 12 h. It was assumed that after this time any residual solvent in the lignite matrix had evaporated.

Fig. 5. shows the % crude wax extracted plotted against time for the four runs carried out with the

Fig 5. Plots of % wax extracted vs time: (+) 1st run, (\square) 2nd. run, (Δ) 3rd. run and (\times) 4th run, toluene at 90°C.

1 kg lignite batch. The total mass of crude wax was obtained by extrapolation of Fig. 6, which

Fig. 6. Exhaustive extraction.

shows the cumulative mass of wax (g) against the number of extractions. Table 9 shows the % yields and the cumulative mass for the four extractions, together with the total mass of crude wax obtained.

TABLE 9—YIELD OF CRUDE WAX FROM EXHAUSTIVE EXTRACTION OF 1 kg OF LIGNITE

Extraction	% Yield crude wax	Cumulative mass (g)
First	10.9	82.21
Second	3.8	107.58
Third	2.5	120.08
Fourth	1.4	126.97
Exhaustive	—	138.0

The total mass of wax of 138 g extracted from the original mass of dry lignite of 829.8 g represents a 16.6% extraction. From Fig. 5 it is clear that the majority (60%) of the wax present in the lignite is extracted by the first contact with toluene. Furthermore, 80–90% of the mass wax extracted during the 3 h run is extracted within the first hour of the extraction.

Conclusion: The following conclusions are made based on the above study: (i) use of a stirred tank system is an acceptable method for wax extraction from Antrim lignite, (ii) toluene is a satisfactory solvent for the extraction of wax from Antrim lignite, (iii) increasing the temperature of the extraction increased the % wax yield but there was a limit on this, (iv) the total crude wax content of Antrim lignite was 16.6% (dry basis), (v) the majority (60%) of wax present in the lignite was extracted by the first 3 h contact with toluene, and (vi) 80–90% of the mass wax extracted during each 3 h run was extracted within the first hour of the extraction.

References

1. "Kirk-Othmer Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology", Wiley-Interscience, 1981, Vol. 14, p. 313.
2. A. GAINES, "Lignite. A Down to Earth fuel; A Guide to Lignite Utilization in Northern Ireland", The Queen's University of Belfast, NI, 1984.
3. B. WHITE, "Lignite: The Facts, the Fears—and the Future", The Belfast Telegraph, 4th. March, 1986.
4. N. G. WAGLE and J. G. KANE, *Chem. Age India*, 1967, **18**, 9.
5. "Thorpe's Dictionary of Applied Chemistry", 1947, Vol. 8.
6. E. DONATH, *Brennstoff Chem.*, 1920, **1**, 86 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1921, **15**, 744).
7. W. SCHNEIDER, *Ges. Abhandl. Kenntn. Kohle*, 1920, **5**, 46, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1923, **42**, 3A.
8. S. SUBRAHMANYAN and A. P. MADHAVAN NAIR, *J. Univ. Madras (B)*, 1957, **27**, 317.
9. E. M. KAMPOURIS, O. CONSTANTINOGLU, N. PROUNIAS and T. SIDEROPOULOS, *Fuel*, 1973, **52**, 47.
10. B. JUDD and R. KEMP, "Wax Extraction from South Island Lignites", Dept. Sci. Ind. Research, New Zealand, 1975, Part 1.
11. WILSON, "Extraction of Montan Wax from Antrim Lignite," Dept. Chem. Eng, Queen's University of Belfast, 1986.
12. A. DAVANKOV and O. A. KONOVALOVA, *Org. Chem. Ind. (USSR)*, 1937, **4**.
13. E. GRAFE, *Braunkohlen-Brsk*, 1921, **29** 297.
14. A. RIEBECCK'SCHER MONTANWERK, Ger. Pat. 509 173/1927.
15. V. I. KRUZNERISOV and N. S. TRUFIMOV, *Ku Acad. Sci. Ukrain SSR*, 1938, **3**.
16. Ger. Pat. 532 212/1927 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1932 **26**, 284).
17. C. M. CAWLEY, J. H. G. CARLILE and C. O. NOAKS, *Petroleum (London)*, 1948, **11**, 77.
18. F. L. KAGANOVICH and V. E. RAKONSKI, *Vestn. Akad. Nauk B, SSR, Ser. Fiz. Tech. Nauk.*, 1958, **117**.
19. H. ALBIN WARTH, "The Chemistry and Technology of Waxes", Reinhold, New York, 1956.